

4:6-DINITRO-*o*-TOLUIDINE: A NEW SYNTHESIS

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During a programme of research on nitration of some iodo compounds in this laboratory (Kapil, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4127), sufficient quantity of 4:6-dinitro-*o*-toluidine was required. Considerable difficulty was experienced when its preparation was undertaken by the partial reduction of 2:4:6-trinitrotoluene (Anschütz and Zimmermann, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 152; Brand and Eisenmenger, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 674); other side-products, such as, 6-nitro-*m*-toluylenediamine (Tiemann, *Ber.*, 1870, 3, 217; Brady *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2264), 2:6-dinitro-*p*-toluidine (Holleman and Boeseken, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1897, 18, 425; Brady *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) and 2:6-dinitro-4-hydroxylaminotoluene (Cohen and Dakin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1257; Anschütz and Zimmermann, *loc. cit.*), were invariably formed during reduction which were difficult to separate. A new method was therefore planned involving the nitration of 4-nitro-*o*-toluidine in concentrated sulphuric acid with fuming nitric acid.

Procedure.—To a solution of 4-nitro-*o*-toluidine (5 g.) in H_2SO_4 (d 1.8, 40 c.c.), cooled to 0° , fuming nitric acid (d 1.5, 5 c.c.) was added dropwise with vigorous shaking; the mixture was then allowed to attain the room temperature (2 hours) and poured on crushed ice. The crude 4:6-dinitro-*o*-toluidine, originally precipitated as a gummy mass, soon solidified, which was filtered, washed well with water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow crystals (3 g.), m.p. 160° . (Found: N, 21.1. Calc. for $C_7H_7O_4N_2$: N, 21.3%).

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